

APPRAISAL OF HOWARD GARDNER'S MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES' (MI) THEORY:
IMPLICATIONS FOR PEDAGOGY AND COUNSELLING PRACTICE IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Over the ages, educators and parents perceived that individual differences in children could also imply differences in learning styles. In keeping with the position that no individual is without some specific gifting, Howard Gardner propounded the Multiple Intelligences Theory in 1983. The MI theory has since been a theme of many research works, conferences and symposia globally. However, the MI theory has not been without its antagonists and challenges in its application to classroom situations are several. Whereas in Europe, North America and parts of Asia, school systems, schools and individual teachers have been working and experimenting to adapt the theory at different levels and scopes in optimizing effective pedagogic service delivery, its application is still green in Nigeria. It is the contention of this author that even though the MI theory is quite desirable in facilitating high learning outcomes and raising education standards, its cost-effectiveness and affordability, especially in developing economies, is questionable. This paper submits, among others, that in applying the MI Theory in therapeutic interventions, the counsellor's versatility is going to be thoroughly challenged.

KEYWORDS: Individual Differences, Multiple Intelligences, Counsellor, Teacher

INTRODUCTION

This paper is an overview of one of the most striking challenges to the traditional scientific view of what constitutes human intelligence and how it can be objectively measured, Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences. Gardner's MI theory has been gaining global prominence through its successful application in a number of experimental educational projects. There are about fifty books on the topic and probably the same number of people who make a living partly from giving talks on the subject (Davies 1996). It is posited that intelligence is not just a one-sided phenomenon but it includes a range of seven distinct groups of skills, talents, and ways of dealing with the world around us (Gardner 1983). By finding methods of developing and measuring each separate type of intelligence, Gardner believes that schools can produce more completely realized individuals and encourage students to develop their fullest possible potential. His ideas have not yet been widely accepted in western education, but they offer a paradigm shift in education service delivery.

The concept of measuring human intelligence along a consistently applied scale is a distinctly twentieth century idea. It was French psychologist Alfred Binet who devised the first widely used test of intelligence in 1905 which the scientific community as a whole came very quickly to accept while refining and adding to the specific methodology for such testing. However, Gardner (1983) arguing that "*reason, intelligence, logic, knowledge are not synonymous. . .*" proposed a view of intelligence that is rapidly being incorporated in school curricula. In his Theory of Multiple Intelligences, Gardner expanded the concept of intelligence to also include such areas as music, spatial relations, and interpersonal knowledge in addition to mathematical and linguistic ability. Gardner defines intelligence as "*the capacity to solve problems or to fashion products that are valued in one or more cultural setting*" (Gardner and Hatch, 1989). Using biological and cultural concepts, he formulated a list of seven intelligences. This outlook on intelligence differs greatly from the traditional view which usually recognizes only two intelligences, the verbal and the mathematical.

The seven (7) intelligences Gardner defines are:

Logical-Mathematical Intelligence

This consists of the ability to detect patterns, reason deductively and think logically. This intelligence is most often associated with scientific and mathematical thinking.

Linguistic Intelligence

This involves having a mastery of language. This intelligence includes the ability to effectively manipulate language to express oneself rhetorically or poetically. It also allows one to use language as a means to remember information.

Spatial Intelligence

This gives one the ability to manipulate and create mental images in order to solve problems. This intelligence is not limited to visual domains-- Gardner notes that spatial intelligence is also formed in blind children.

Musical Intelligence

It encompasses the capability to recognize and compose musical pitches, tones, and rhythms. (Auditory functions are required for a person to develop this intelligence in relation to pitch and tone, but it is not needed for the knowledge of rhythm.)

Bodily-Kinaesthetic Intelligence

This is the ability to use one's mental abilities to coordinate one's own bodily movements. This intelligence challenges the popular belief that mental and physical activities are unrelated.

The Personal Intelligences

It includes interpersonal intelligence (which is the ability to understand and discern the feelings and intentions of others) and intrapersonal intelligence that is the ability to understand one's own feelings and motivations, indeed ability to master oneself. These two intelligences are separate from each other. Nevertheless, because of their close association in most cultures, they are often linked together.

Although the intelligences are anatomically separated from each other, Gardner claims that the seven intelligences very rarely operate independently. Gardner submits that the intelligences are used complementarily and concurrently as individuals develop skills or solve problems. For example, a dancer can do well in his art only if he has

1) strong musical intelligence to understand the rhythm and variations of the music, 2) interpersonal intelligence to understand how he can inspire or emotionally move his audience through his rhythmic movements, as well as 3) bodily-kinaesthetic intelligence to provide him with the agility and coordination to complete the movements successfully.

Basis for Intelligence

The position of Gardner is that there are both biological and cultural bases for the multiple intelligences. Indeed, neurobiological research indicates that learning is an outcome of the modifications in the synaptic connections between cells. Primary elements of different types of learning are found in particular areas of the brain where corresponding transformations have occurred. Thus, various types of learning result in synaptic connections in different areas of the brain. For example, injury to the Broca's area of the brain will result in the loss of one's ability to verbally communicate using proper syntax. Nevertheless, this injury will not remove the patient's understanding of correct grammar and word usage. Scientists used to think that the brain was hardwired at a very early age and set for the rest of life (that is what is called pruning). However, this assumption is only partially true today. Pruning does take place at an early age, but research has confirmed that nerves continue to grow throughout one's life. It is quite possible to teach old dogs a few new tricks after all! This is a huge discovery and has implications for life-long learning.

As with any new learning, frustration seems to follow, as in the case of learning to drive stick-shift (manual) car. There is a period of time when the body is unable to do what the mind wants it to do. Individuals get emotional. From brain research, it is established that when we get emotional about a task we are involved in learning. Brain research has confirmed that emotions are linked to learning by assisting us in recall of memories that are stored in our central nervous system. Emotions originate in the midbrain or what has been termed the limbic system and the neo-mammalian brain. Sensory information is relayed to the *thalamus* in the midbrain, which acts as a relay station to the sensory cortex, auditory cortex, etc. When sensory information reaches the *amygdala*, another structure in the midbrain, that sensory information is evaluated as either a threat or not, creating the familiar fight or flight response

– the physiological response of stress. This information is only then relayed to the frontal cortex, our higher cognitive functions, where we take the appropriate action.

How does information from the midbrain reach the frontal cortex? Chemicals and neurotransmitters are released into the endocrine system which is connected to synapses, altering, colouring and intensifying our conscious experience of a situation. Emotions aid in memory retention (learning) of this situation as being good or bad. Decreasing threat ("driving our fear", mistrust, anxiety and competition) through cooperation, providing safe places, and providing a motivational climate for positive emotions ensure that learning will be retained.

However, brain research also suggests that the brain learns best when confronted with a balance between stress and comfort; between high challenge and low threat. The brain normally needs some challenge, or some environmental press that generates stress as described above to activate emotions and learning. This is because stress motivates a survival imperative in the brain. Too much stress and anxiety shuts down opportunities for learning. When there is too little stress, the brain becomes too relaxed and comfortable to become actively engaged. The phrase used to describe the brain state for optimal learning is that of relaxed-alertness. Practically speaking, this means that educators need to create places that are not only safe to learn, but also spark some emotional interest through celebrations and interactions.

Another general finding from brain research is that the brain is a pattern maker. Pattern making is a pleasing emotional experience for the brain. The brain takes great pleasure in taking random and chaotic information and ordering it. The implications for learning and instruction is that presenting a learner with random and unordered information provides the maximum opportunity for the brain to order this information and form meaningful patterns that will be remembered, thus, will be learned. Setting up a learning environment in this way mirrors real life that is often random and chaotic.

The brain, when allowed to express its pattern-making behaviour, creates coherency and meaning. Learning is best accomplished when the learning activity is connected directly to physical experience. Individuals remember best when facts and skills are embedded in natural, spatial memory, in real-life activity, in experiential learning. We learn by doing. Applying findings of neuroscience related to coherency and meaning may suggest that learning could be facilitated in an environment of total immersion in a multitude of complex interactive experiences. This could also include traditional instructional methods of lecture and analysis as part of this larger experience.

Interaction of the brain with its environment suggests that the more enriched environment, the more enriched brain. It has been suggested that an enriched environment can contribute up to a 25% increase in the number of brain connections both early and later in life (Kotulak 1996). The environments we live in need to allow for active manipulation.

To summarize, there are at least twelve principles of brain-compatible learning that have emerged from brain research.

1. Uniqueness – every single brain is totally unique.
2. Impact of threat or high stress can alter and impair learning and even kill brain cells
3. Emotions are critical to learning – they drive our attention, health, learning, meaning and memory.
4. Information is stored and retrieved through multiple memory and neural pathways
5. All learning is mind-body – movement, foods, attentional cycles, drugs and chemicals all have powerful modulating effects on learning.
6. The brain is a complex and adaptive system – effective change involves the entire complex system
7. Patterns and programmes drive our understanding – intelligence is the ability to elicit and to construct useful patterns.
8. The brain is meaning-driven – This means that meaning is more important to the brain than information.
9. Learning is often rich and non-conscious – people process both parts and wholes simultaneously and are affected a great deal by peripheral influences.
10. The brain develops better in concert with other brains – intelligence is valued in the context of the society in which we live.

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12. The brain develops with various stages of readiness.
13. Enrichment – the brain can grow new connections at any age. Complex, challenging experiences with feedback are best. Cognitive skills develop better with music and motor skills.

In addition to biology, Gardner (1983) argues that culture also plays a large role in the development of the intelligences. All societies value different types of intelligences. The cultural value placed upon the ability to perform certain tasks provides the motivation to become skilled in those areas. Thus, while particular intelligences might be highly evolved in many people of one culture, those same intelligences might not be as developed in the individuals of another. For instance, it is suggested that given their peculiar nutrition and culture of martial arts, Asians are generally fitter and may perform better than Africans in sports such as karate, taekwondo and even football. On the other hand, Africans seem to be better developed in the performing arts and entertainment. This is quite evident in the plethora of blacks in dance, drama, music and folklore. An unconfirmed position is that nutrition may also account for individual differences in intelligence.

Implications of Multiple Intelligences for Education Service Delivery

Accepting Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences has several implications for teachers in terms of classroom instruction. The theory states that all seven intelligences are needed to productively function in society. Teachers, therefore, should think of all intelligences as equally important. This is in great contrast to traditional education systems which typically place a strong emphasis on the development and use of verbal and mathematical intelligences. Thus, in applying the Theory of Multiple Intelligences, educators should seek to recognize and teach to a broader range of talents and skills.

Another implication is that teachers would need to structure the presentation of material in a style which engages most or all of the intelligences. For example, when teaching about the revolutionary war, a teacher can show students battle maps, play revolutionary war songs, organize a role play of the signing of the Declaration of Independence, and have the students read a novel about life during that period. This kind of presentation not only excites students about learning, but it also allows a teacher to reinforce the same material in a variety of ways. By activating a wide assortment of intelligences, teaching in this manner can facilitate a deeper understanding of the subject material.

The teacher must have it settled in his heart that everyone is born possessing several intelligences. Nevertheless, all students will come into the classroom with different levels of developed intelligences. This means that each child will have his own unique set of intellectual strengths and weaknesses. These sets determine how easy (or difficult) it is for a student to learn information when it is presented in a particular manner. This is commonly referred to as a learning style. Many learning styles can be found within one classroom. Therefore, it is impossible, as well as impractical, for a teacher to accommodate every lesson to all of the learning styles found within the classroom. Nevertheless the teacher can show students how to use their more developed intelligences to assist in the understanding of a subject which normally employs their weaker intelligences (Lazear, 1992). For example, the teacher can suggest that an especially musically intelligent child learn about the competitive sport of Fencing by making up a song about what happened.

The MI theory has been adapted and interpreted by many intermediate writers who have made it easy for both teachers and parents to see the value of the concept and its applicability to uses in the classroom. This broad range of interpretations at intermediary levels makes related techniques easy to understand and use by both student teachers and practising educators. Also, due to the proliferation of medial interpretations, related conference presentations and accessible classroom materials (in addition to associated articles for parents in current media in the western and eastern worlds) MI has become so popular that the concept has become much like a grassroots movement.

Also, the MI theory offers teachers assistance in helping students become empowered learners by extending and promoting cognitive bridging techniques based on the seven intelligences; by fostering deep metacognitive understanding; and by advancing suggestions for a broad array of diversified study skills techniques. Thus, it also aids teachers in easily creating more personalized and diversified instructional experiences.

It is instructive to note that the MI theory helps teachers explain and promote understanding at intrapersonal, interpersonal and cultural levels.

The MI theory taps into students' intrinsic levels of motivation through natural talents, thus helps teachers construct self-motivating educational experiences and ones which help promote the concept of flow in the classroom.

The MI theory may validate teachers' insightful and intuitive assessments of students' natural talents and offers them justifications and assistance in creating related personalized educational accommodations and experiences.

It also provides teachers, parents and students with a more extensive and egalitarian conceptualization of giftedness. As Gardner (1983, 1993) repeatedly points out, perceptions of intelligence are often limited to tests which assess verbal-linguistic or mathematical-logical skills. Historically, programmes that service students who are designated as gifted are reflective of this narrow cultural and educational mindset. MI precepts categorically broaden categories of giftedness. Thus, programmes based on MI have the potential to include students having gifts, or combinations of gifts, from Gardner's other designated categories--bodily-kinaesthetic, musical, spatial, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and soon to be elaborated, naturalistic intelligence. This broadened array greatly appeals to those teachers and parents who hold a more egalitarian or comprehensive view that every child has a gift or combined gifts.

Through creating educational experiences based on natural talents and gifts, teachers are more likely to increase opportunities whereby students can become actively engaged in learning experiences that are pleasurable, heightened or magnified. Such experiences can be highly motivational

Part of the artistry of teaching revolves around gut feelings and keen observational skills. However, sometimes teachers operating at levels of intuitive artistry are made to feel that their opinions and assessments of students are trivial, wrong or less valid when compared to profiles developed from verifiable and quantifiable types of traditional measures. In this context, knowledge of MI's definitions of intelligence helps to validate many teachers' qualitative or intuitive assessments of students.

While the answers to understanding the educational popularity of MI Theory fully undoubtedly lie in many directions, the key issues to comprehending the theory's burgeoning acceptance seem to be related to the basic needs of teachers as they try to create more inclusive, affective and effective instruction. These basic teaching needs are primarily related to promoting understanding and appreciation among students, to creating classrooms where learners experience a sense of loving and belonging, to issues of fostering pupils' esteem, personal intellectual empowerment and self-motivation, and to helping teachers achieve more diversified instructional techniques. Simply, MI Theory is getting more relevant because it helps educators meet the needs of many different types of learners easily, and because it reflects teachers' and parents' deeply rooted philosophical beliefs that all children possess gifts and that part of the most important mission of schools is to foster positive personal development. Thus, teachers understanding and using MI theory, and its related educational frameworks and explanations of diversity, are being transformed into teachers who understand human patterns, human diversity and human learning at better, deeper, and more comprehensive levels.

MI Application in Nigeria & Implications for Counselling Practice

Generally, applying MI theory in schools could be quite expensive and demanding. Instead of the traditional method, the teacher must now begin to teach in seven (7) different ways and must seek to accommodate every child in his teaching. This would definitely put some strain on the teacher but over some time, with versatility, he would be able to cope and really enjoy the whole experience. This would undoubtedly enhance academic performance of the students across board.

However, there are several barriers to the successful application and acceptance of the MI theory in schools.

1. Many parents may not value the MI approach to teaching since they may not understand how it can help their children to be better individual.
2. Educators, particularly administrators, are usually focused on short-term gains and standardized test results which centre on scholastic intelligences.

3. Teachers may be quite reluctant to expend the time and energy necessary to bring MI to life in their classrooms.

The good news is each of these obstacles can be addressed.

The counsellor holds the ace in facilitating more positive school-community relations. The counsellor is in the best position to help individuals develop positive self-concept and self-image. The counsellor is trained to help teachers and parents to optimise the parent-teacher conferences and open days. Schools have often sought to help students develop a sense of accomplishment and self-confidence. Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences provides a theoretical foundation for recognizing the different abilities and talents of students. This theory acknowledges that while all students may not be verbally or mathematically gifted, children may have an expertise in other areas, such as music, spatial relations, or interpersonal knowledge. Approaching and assessing learning in this manner allows a wider range of students to successfully participate in classroom learning. The guidance counsellor would need to be up-to-date and quite versatile in the use of psychological inventories and tests in class placement and career advice for individual students.

Parent education, something which should be highly valued in any school, becomes a major priority in an MI school. Since it is certain that none of the students' parents will have attended an MI school, educators need to help them understand how the intelligences are used and that their children are learning. (Oddly, sometimes parents are the most sceptical about the soundness of an academic program because their children tell them that school is fun!) Signs in the halls, explanations on student work that is posted, weekly letters from the teachers and principal, parent education evenings, student portfolios, exhibitions and performances (PEPs) and framing parent-teacher conferences around the intelligences all contribute to parents understanding. It is not enough to entertain parents; they must be educated so that they understand how MI is used.

As logical and simple as all of these steps may sound, however, they are difficult to do. This is primarily because most educators don't appreciate the value of educating parents. Too often the parent-teacher relationship becomes us versus them. Teachers, often with justification, fear that more parent communications will lead to more parent criticism. And all too often, when teachers do try to involve and educate their students' parents, the parents do not respond.

To each of these hesitations, it could be argued that an MI approach facilitates teacher-parent communication. Parents who are critical of schools are often so because they are wary. Simply put, they aren't sure that their child is learning (or, worse, they know – they've been told – that their child isn't learning). When parents view their children's progress through an MI lens, however, the gains are quite obvious. By reviewing the contents of a child's portfolio, for example, or by attending (or seeing videotapes of) student presentations and performances, the gains are clear and striking. Over time, the enthusiasm and excitement about learning that is generated by an MI approach will result in students doing better on traditional measures as well.

Some teachers, of course, try to involve parents. They do all the right things, but still, despite their efforts, few parents come to school or get involved. It isn't that these parents love their children any less. It could be that these parents are unable to get away from work, that they don't have the flexibility to be present during the day (which is why sending home videos of students' performances and progress is good). But it may also be that these parents, themselves, struggled in school that for them, walking into the building is a reminder of their personal frustration and failure. (This is compounded if their children are having school difficulties. For regardless of how well we present our concerns, parents who hear that their children are failing also hear that they are failing as parents.) But by using MI, by offering parent nights in which the parents can engage in the same activities that students do during the day – use their intelligences – we can begin to chip away at some of the fear or cynicism that parents bring to the table.

CONCLUSION

As the education system has stressed the importance of developing mathematical and linguistic intelligences, it often bases student success only on the measured skills in those two intelligences. Supporters of Gardner's Theory of

Multiple Intelligences believe that this emphasis is unfair. Children whose musical intelligences are highly developed, for example, may be overlooked for gifted programs or may be placed in a special education class because they do not have the required math or language scores. Teachers must seek to assess their students' learning in ways which will give an accurate overview of their strengths and weaknesses.

As children do not learn in the same way, they cannot be assessed in a uniform fashion. Therefore, it is important that a teacher create an "intelligence profiles" for each student. Knowing how each student learns will allow the teacher to properly assess the child's progress (Lazear, 1992). This individualized evaluation practice will allow a teacher to make more informed decisions on what to teach and how to present information.

Traditional tests (e.g. multiple choice, short answer, essay. . .) require students to show their knowledge in a predetermined manner. Supporters of Gardner's theory claim that a better approach to assessment is to allow students to explain the material in their own ways using the different intelligences. Preferred assessment methods include student portfolios, independent projects, student journals, and assigning creative tasks. An excellent source for a more in-depth discussion on these different evaluation practices is Lazear (1992).

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